

We provide potential prompts for zero-shot and few-shot medical question-answering tasks.

Table 1: Zero-shot prompt example.

System Message:

As a skilled medical domain expert, you are tasked to analyze multiple-choice questions for the United States Medical License Exams, and select the correct answer.

User Message:

Your task is to select the correct answer from the provided options and explanation that guided your choice. Your response must only contain the following JSON format:{"correct_option_index": "index of the correct option (A-D)", "explanation": "explanation for the choice step by step"}.

Now, give your answer for the following question.

—Question—

...

—Options—

...

Table 2: Few-shot prompt example.

System Message:

As a skilled medical domain expert, you are tasked to analyze multiple-choice questions for the United States Medical License Exams, and select the correct answer.

User Message:

Your task is to select the correct answer from the provided options and explanation that guided your choice. Your response must only contain the following JSON format:{"correct_option_index": "index of the correct option (A-D)", "explanation": "explanation for the choice step by step"}.

Here are three examples:

—Example 1—

—Question—

A 22-year-old male marathon runner presents to the office with the complaint of right-sided rib pain when he runs long distances. Physical examination reveals normal heart and lung findings and an exhalation dysfunction at ribs 4-5 on the right. Which of the following muscles or muscle groups will be most useful in correcting this dysfunction utilizing a direct method?

—Options—

A. anterior scalene B. latissimus dorsi C. pectoralis minor D. quadratus lumborum

—Answer—

{"correct_option_index": "C", "explanation": "We refer to Wikipedia articles on medicine for help. Among the options, only pectoralis minor muscle origins from the outer surfaces of the 3rd to 5th ribs."}

—Example 2—

—Question—

A 36-year-old male presents to the office with a 3-week history of low back pain. He denies any recent trauma but says that he climbs in and out of his truck numerous times a day for his job. Examination of the patient in the prone position reveals a deep sacral sulcus on the left, a posterior inferior lateral angle on the right, and a lumbosacral junction that springs freely on compression. The most likely diagnosis is

—Options—

A. left-on-left sacral torsion B. left-on-right sacral torsion C. right unilateral sacral flexion D. right-on-right sacral torsion

—Answer—

{"correct_option_index": "D", "explanation": "We refer to Wikipedia articles on medicine for help. The deep sulcus on the left, a posterior ILA on the right, with a negative spring test suggests a right-on-right sacral torsion. All other options have a deep sulcus on the right."}

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User Message:

—Example 3—

—Question—

A 44-year-old man comes to the office because of a 3-day history of sore throat, nonproductive cough, runny nose, and frontal headache. He says the headache is worse in the morning and ibuprofen does provide some relief. He has not had shortness of breath. Medical history is unremarkable. He takes no medications other than the ibuprofen for pain. Vital signs are temperature 37.4 °C (99.4 °F), pulse 88/min, respirations 18/min, and blood pressure 120/84 mm Hg. Examination of the nares shows erythematous mucous membranes. Examination of the throat shows erythema and follicular lymphoid hyperplasia on the posterior oropharynx. There is no palpable cervical adenopathy. Lungs are clear to auscultation. Which of the following is the most likely cause of this patient's symptoms?

—Options—

A. Allergic rhinitis B. Epstein-Barr virus C. Mycoplasma pneumonia D. Rhinovirus

—Answer—

{“correct_option_index”：“D”, “explanation”：“We refer to Wikipedia articles on medicine for help. The symptoms, especially the headache, suggest that the most likely cause is Rhinovirus. Epstein-Barr virus will cause swollen lymph nodes but there is no palpable cervical adenopathy. Lungs are clear to auscultation suggests it's not Mycoplasma pneumonia.”}

Now, give your answer for the following question.

—Question—

...

—Options—

...
